

ASIAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH CONFERENCE (AMRC) 2025 PROCEEDINGS

Theme: *“Convergence of Knowledge: Influencing the
Future through Multidisciplinary Approaches”*

JUNE 14, 2025 | 8:00 A.M. - 5:00 P.M.

Hybrid platform

Venue:

**The Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences,
Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University
1 U Thong Nok Rd. Dusit, Dusit District, Bangkok, Thailand**

“We Reflect. We Write. We Transform Lives.”

COYPRIGHT PAGE

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ASIAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH CONFERENCE (AMRC) 2025 PROCEEDINGS

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The Conference Committee

DR. ETHEL REYES CHUA
Conference Chair

DR. ALFE M. SOLINA
Conference Co-Chair

DR. MA. LEAH P. ULANDAY
Conference Co-Chair

DR. ANGVARRAH LIEUNGNAPAR
*Chairperson, Venue Organizing Committee
& Head, Technical Working Group*

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Philippine Christian University
Emilio Aguinaldo College -Cavite
Francisco E. Barzaga Memorial School
Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE)
Northwest Samar State University
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Message from the Chief Executive Officer

Respected ladies and gentlemen!

I welcome you to the Asian Multidisciplinary Research Conference (AMRC) 2025. This yearly event is evidence of our shared dedication to promoting communication, creativity, and teamwork within the academic community.

This year, we are living at a critical crossroads. The fast advancement of technology and the changing social and economic environments offer possibilities and problems. Our duty as industrial relations leaders and practitioners is to guide this transition with honesty and vision, ensuring that the future workforce is prepared to succeed in a changing environment.

The theme *“Convergence of Knowledge: Influencing the Future Through Multidisciplinary Approaches”* embodies our shared goal of building a future where advancement benefits everyone through exploration, networking, and sustainability. Over the next few hours, the varied roster of speakers and panelists will share their perspectives and experiences. Their knowledge will surely stimulate and test our ability to critically consider how industrial relations affect long-term, sustainable progress.

I urge all of you to actively engage in the discussions and virtual networking opportunities as we begin the journey together. This conference's real worth lies in the ideas shared and the relationships formed; these may lead to significant changes in our areas.

Finally, I sincerely thank the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences of Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand, for giving us the best opportunity to use their venue, facilities, and equipment to make this event possible. Without them, the TWG would never have seen the beautiful places in Thailand—my special thanks to the venue's local organizer, Dr. Lieungnapar Angvarrah.

Let's take advantage of this chance to grow, work together, and create a better future. I appreciate everything and hope the conference is fruitful and motivational for everyone. Welcome to AMRC 2025!

Mr. Jerome N. Chua
CEO, EduHeart Book Publishing &
Training and Development Services

Welcome Message

DR. ETHEL REYES-CHUA
President, Eduheart Book Publishing

Honorable Guests, Respected Research Enthusiasts, Students, and Professional Researchers!

This assembly of distinguished intellectuals from various locations offers a unique chance to participate in thought-provoking discussions, exchange creative ideas, and open fresh perspectives in our shared pursuit of knowledge and advancement.

This conference reflects our common commitment to tackling the pressing issues that the environment is currently experiencing. As we gather here, we are reminded that our diversity strengthens us. Because of the many viewpoints and knowledge everyone brings to this conference, we can promote understanding and create comprehensive plans that benefit everyone. We can go in the right direction and create a better future if we pool our knowledge and work together.

For the next few hours, we will have the chance to listen to professional and student researchers, participate in enlightening discussions, and attend stimulating sessions with the keynote, plenary, and resource speakers. These discussions aim to sharpen our minds, broaden our perspectives, and motivate us to act. I urge every one of you to make the most of these chances, cooperate with your colleagues, and share your ideas.

Let's seize this chance to collaborate, learn from one another, and create sustainable solutions that will have a long-lasting effect on the globe. I do not doubt that this conference will result in essential breakthroughs and long-lasting collaborations.

Thank you, and I hope the conference is successful, motivating, and exciting for all of you.

Message from the Conference Co-Chairperson

Dr. Alfe M. Solina

*Consultant
EduHeart Book Publishing
PHILIPPINES*

It gives me great pleasure that EduHeart Book Publishing and the EduHeart Training and Development Services are organizing the Asian Multidisciplinary Research Conference (AMRC) 2025. This conference will provide a forum for national and international professionals, students, academicians, and researchers to interact and be involved in research development and innovation. Such event benefits students, teachers, and researchers immensely and broaden their knowledge, work ideas, and global experience. I sincerely appreciate the modest and professional efforts of EduHeart in providing a platform for students, academicians, and researchers to share their ideas and research outcomes through the conference forum. I give my best wishes to all presenters, attendees, and the organizing committee to make this event a grand success.

Conference Co-Chairperson's Profile

Dr. Ma. Leah P. Ulanday

Dr. Ma. Leah Pacleb-Ulanday is currently serving as the Campus Administrator and a full-time faculty member of Cavite State University- Silang Campus. She served as the Head of the Office of Student Affairs and Services, Research Coordinator of the Department of Arts and Sciences, Coordinator of the National Service Training Program, and one of the Gender and Development Focal Persons of the University. Presently, she is designated as the Principal of CvSU- Silang Laboratory Science High School and Research Coordinator of Teacher Education Department. She has over 10 years of experience in the academe and 2 years' experience in clinical settings. She has written several book chapters and research through personal and interdisciplinary research through academic collaboration, presented at local and international conferences as well as published in Scopus, Web of Science, and ISI-indexed journals. Currently, she is conducting research about inclusive education in the 5th District of Cavite and examining the different literature on the application of expert systems with artificial intelligence in the educational and medical fields. Moreover, she was recently elected as a Regular Member of Department of Science and Technology- National Research Council of the Philippines (DOST-NRCP) Division 1 (Governmental, Educational and International Policy). She was awarded a Faculty Recognition for Research in October 2021 by the Central Student Government of CvSU- Silang. A recipient of CHED- Scholarships for Instructors' Knowledge Advancement Program (SIKAP) in 2021. Book Chapter Author of the Year (2023) by the Eduheart Book Publishing Inc. "Gintong Butil ng Carmona" Plaque of Recognition Award in June 2017 and June 2024. She had over 133 Article Citations and h-index = 4 as Verified in Google Scholar. An esteemed speaker and lecturer, a regular member of the International Multidisciplinary Organization for Research and Extension (IMORE), Consultant & Author of Eduheart Book Publishing, Peer Reviewer of International and Web of Science Indexed Journal, GAD Advocate, Extensionist, Registered Nurse, and a Licensed professional teacher.

Keynote Speaker's Profile

Prof. Mario Pace

**Head of Department for Languages and Humanities Education
University of Malta, Malta**

Prof. Mario Pace is an Associate Professor of Italian and Head of the Department of Languages and Humanities in Education within the Faculty of Education of the University of Malta. He is responsible for the training and formation of teachers of Italian as a foreign language. Besides language teaching methodology, his main areas of interest include second language acquisition, foreign language teaching and learning, and the teaching of foreign languages for specific purposes. He is also a Visiting Professor in a number of Universities across Europe. For a number of years he was consultant to the Ministry of Education in Malta on the teaching and learning of foreign languages in compulsory education. He has participated in conferences both in Europe and the USA and is the author of several chapters in books as well as academic papers in peer reviewed journals. He is also the author of the book entitled *Marco Largi ovvero Carlo Magri drammaturgo maltese 1617 1693 Vita e opera* published in 2018. He received the prestigious award of Cavaliere dell'Ordine della Stella d'Italia "(given by the President of the Italian Republic Sergio Mattarella in recognition of his significant contribution towards the enhancement of the teaching and learning of Italian as a foreign language in Maltese schools and other educational institutions.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Dr. Virginia Dulay-Akiate
Former Regional Director
Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Region IV-A
Philippines

Dr. Virginia Dulay-Akiate, CESO III, is a former Regional Director of the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Region IV-A and a Special Assistant to the Chairman of the Higher Education Institution Affairs of the Commission on Higher Education Central Office. She got her BS Education degree from Saint Louis University as an International College Woman Scholar. Her Master's and Doctorate degrees were obtained from the University of Baguio and Baguio Central University, respectively, where she was a Professional Chair and Faculty Scholar. Among her notable certificates of training were: Higher Education Management by Ateneo de Manila, Global Academic Leadership Program by Asian Institute of Management, and other academic collaborations here and abroad. She rose from the ranks, receiving citations as faculty member, Dean of Education, Liberal Arts and Graduate School, and Director of Research and External Affairs. After passing the Career Executive Service Officer Eligibility, she was appointed by the President of the Philippines as Regional Director and has been assigned to various regions of the country. For 42 years in the government service, she firmly believes that PUBLIC SERVICE is a PUBLIC TRUST.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Dr. Elbert M. Galas

**University President, Pangasinan State University
Pangasinan, Philippines**

Dr. Elbert Manangan Galas is currently serving as the 7th President of Pangasinan State University. His areas of specialization include information technology, information systems, quality assurance, quality management systems, and educational leadership. Before he was elected University President, he held numerous designations in PSU, such as: IT Program Chairperson, Director for Quality Assurance, Campus Executive Director, Vice President for Quality Assurance, and Vice President for Administration and Linkages. As a consistent CHED scholar, Dr. Galas earned his Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) in 2003 at the PSU - Urdaneta Campus. He finished his Master of Information Systems (MIS) in 2010 at the University of the Philippines-Open University, Los Baños, Laguna, and his Doctor of Information Technology (DIT) in 2020 at the Technological Institute of the Philippines as a CHED K to 12 scholar. Dr. Galas is a researcher, author, editor, subject matter expert, instructional designer, publishing specialist, and educator.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Rebecca D. Miranda, CPA, DBA
Vice President for Academic Affairs
Emilio Aguinaldo College – Cavite
Dasmaringas, Cavite, Philippines

Dr. Rebecca Miranda is engaged with Emilio Aguinaldo College, Cavite, where she serves as the Vice President for Academic Affairs and Quality Management Representative. She has been actively involved in the Philippine higher education sector. She has 25 years of experience in administrative leadership, including as the Vice President for Academic Affairs of the University of Baguio.

As an educator and scholar, Dr. Miranda has taught undergraduate and graduate courses in Accountancy and Business Administration. She has also mentored numerous research projects that have contributed to evidence-based practices and local development.

Currently, she is involved in projects aligned with CHED's internationalization and quality assurance thrusts. She serves as an Accreditor of the Philippine Association and Universities Commission on Accreditation. She is also a member of the Philippine Institute of Certified Public Accountants and the Association of Certified Public Accountants in Education, contributing to policy and advocacy initiatives in Philippine education.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Dr. Adrian Lawrence P. Carvajal
Supervising Professional Regulations Officer
Central Office- International Development Division (IDD)
Professional Regulation Commission (PRC), Manila, Philippines

Dr. Adrian Lawrence P. Carvajal is a dynamic educator, research leader, and global consultant whose professional journey spans over twenty years of exemplary service in academia, public administration, and international development. A multi-awarded scholar and speaker, Dr. Carvajal is widely recognized for his trailblazing contributions in research, leadership, and innovation, bridging local insights with global best practices. He currently holds the position of **Supervising Professional Regulations Officer** at the **International Development Division of the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC)**, where he plays a pivotal role in international negotiations and policymaking, particularly in **professional qualifications recognition and cross-border collaboration**.

Dr. Carvajal has led and contributed to **multi-sectoral research initiatives**, including those funded by **USAID, AUSAID, and CHED**, focusing on **inclusive development, technical education, labor market alignment, and community empowerment**. His thought leadership has helped shape responsive policies and capacity-building programs for underserved and priority populations, including persons with disabilities and low-income communities. Internationally, he served as a **Research Consultant in Dubai** on e-governance and institutional transformation, and as **Book Consultant and Senior Project Manager for Chanthology Ltd., United Kingdom**, where he helped conceptualize, review, and publish educational and leadership titles for global audiences.

An esteemed author and editor, he is the **Editor-in-Chief of the International Journal of Open-access, Interdisciplinary and New Educational Discoveries (iJOINED)** and serves on the editorial boards of numerous academic journals. He is also a sought-after mentor for thesis writing, academic publishing, and organizational leadership—guiding emerging scholars and professionals across sectors.

Dr. Carvajal has been honored with numerous accolades, including **Outstanding Author of the Year, International Excellence in Research and Leadership, Global Outstanding Teacher, Most Outstanding Research Advocate, and Best Paper and Best Presenter** at national and international conferences. He is the author of several acclaimed books, including *The Road to Reflective Leadership*, *The Reflective Leader's Handbook*, *The True Leadership Edge*, and *Positive Risking*. Each offers practical insights rooted in his extensive research and leadership experience.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Napasri Suwanajote, PhD

**Dean of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University
Bangkok, Thailand**

Dr. Napasri Suwanajote is the Dean of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences at Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University (SSRU), Thailand, and also serves as Director of the King Sejong Institute Bangkok 2. She holds a PhD in Linguistics, an MA in English Education, and a Bachelor of Science degree, with strong academic and practical expertise in cross-cultural communication and language pedagogy.

With over 20 years of experience, Dr. Suwanajote is a professional interpreter and translator specializing in Korean–Thai–English interpretation. She has worked with government agencies, international NGOs, global corporations, and the entertainment industry. She is also a sought-after guest speaker in multiculturalism, educational development, English for communication, and Korean language and interpretation.

Her academic career includes teaching undergraduate and graduate courses in English for Specific Purposes (ESP) and linguistics and leading interdisciplinary curriculum development. Her research interests include multiculturalism, digital humanities, and the application of AI in language learning and assessment. She has received institutional funding for projects such as developing a digital sign language dictionary and regional youth empowerment through creative cultural content.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Dr. Montarat Rungruangthum
Research Consultant, Faculty of Liberal Arts
Rajamangala University of Technology Phra Nakhon
Thailand

She has a doctorate in Applied Linguistics from King Mongkut's University of Technology Thonburi (KMUTT). She works as an English teacher, researcher, and teacher trainer at Rajamangala University of Technology Phra Nakhon. Her research interests include educational technology, text analysis, English language teaching, and social psychology. She has recently received the Outstanding Researcher Award in Humanities and Social Sciences for Research Utilization and the Distinguished Teacher of Innovations.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Dr. Rosalinda G. Cochico
Chairperson, TVLE
Pangasinan State University - Lingayen Campus
Lingayen, Pangasinan, Philippines

Dr. Rosalinda G. Cochico is currently serving as the *Chairperson* for the TVLE program. She is a faculty member at Pangasinan State University specializing in *Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Education (TVLE)*. She holds a Bachelor of Secondary Education, a Master's in Education, and a Doctorate in Education, all with majors in Technology and Livelihood Education. Dr. Cochico's expertise extends to community engagement and research in TVLE, significantly impacting the teaching of TLE in higher education through her various courses and contributions.

Resource Speaker's Profile

Dr. Alfe M. Solina

**Chairperson, Management Department
Cavite State University – Imus Campus
Imus City, Cavite, Philippines**

Dr. Alfe M. Solina is an author/writer, editor, and subject matter specialist registered with the National Book Development Board in the Philippines. She has produced, co-authored, and edited educational materials and books, and published research studies on management, business, economics, psychology, education, engineering, and information technology.

Her presence in various fora in Singapore; Thailand; Hongkong; Seattle, USA; Seoul, South Korea; along with her international management trainings in Germany; Italy; and Vietnam offered her precious opportunities to be invited as conference speaker, advisory board member, session chair, evaluator, reviewer and as panel for paper presenters from University of the Philippines; University of Waterloo Canada; New York University; Stanford University Business School and Harvard University Business School.

She currently supervises the Graduate School Learning Center and the Department of Management at Cavite State University's Imus Campus in the City of Imus, Cavite, Philippines.

She completed her master's degree in business administration from Ateneo de Manila University as a World Bank scholar, and her Doctor in Business Administration from Polytechnic University of the Philippines in Manila.

Session Chairs/Moderators and Technical Support

On-Site

<u>CLUSTER</u>	<u>SESSION CHAIRS</u>	<u>MODERATOR/TECHNICAL SUPPORT</u>
1 EDUCATION/TVLE/ HUMANITIES/SOCIAL SCIENCES/OTHERS	Dr. Napasri Suwanajote Dr. Rosalinda G. Cochico Ms. Lilibeth S. Tiongson	Dr. Ma. Glenda M. Mendoza
2 ENGINEERING/ICT/BUSINESS	Dr. Priscila R. Castro Dr. Mellie Guico	Ms. Elaine Jairusse R. Capellan
3 STUDENT CATEGORY	Dr. Roldan D. Atienza Dr. Agnes Arellano	Dr. Isagani Y. Busito

On-Line

<u>CLUSTER</u>	<u>SESSION CHAIRS</u>	<u>MODERATOR</u>	<u>TECHNICAL SUPPORT</u>
1 EDUCATION/TVLE/ HUMANITIES/SOCIAL SCIENCES/OTHERS	Dr. Phillip G. Queroda Dr. Amelita M. De Vera Dr. Ma. Christine Soroten	Ms. Maria Virginia A. Fontanos	Ms. Melody A. Agustin
2 ENGINEERING/ICT/ BUSINESS	Asst. Prof. Sixto N. Ras, Jr. Dr. Catherine V. Queroda Dr. Renato E. Salcedo Dr. Jessica James Paiso	Ms. Mary Ann C. Soriano	Mr. Albert P. Ragasa
3 STUDENT CATEGORY	Dr. Baby Kharen A. Cristal Dr. Liane Vina G. Ocampo Asst. Prof. Maryann H. Lanuza	Dr. Vladimir Marie E. Cabutotan	Ms. Noemi C. Orlanda

ASIAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH CONFERENCE (AMRC) 2025

June 14, 2025 (Saturday)

8:00-5:00 p.m.

Hybrid

Theme: "Convergence of Knowledge: Influencing the Future Through Multidisciplinary Approaches"

1. **Description:** The AMRC 2025 is a learning platform in which scholars, practitioners, graduate students, and professionals in Asia and worldwide convene to share breakthrough research, foster cross-disciplinary collaboration, and address the world's most pressing challenges. AMRC 2025, with the theme "*Convergence of Knowledge: Influencing the Future Through Multidisciplinary Approaches*" will unite a range of research disciplines to converge towards the evolution of sustainable solutions that will nurture creative concepts for a better tomorrow. This will also feature keynote addresses, panel discussions, research presentations, and fantastic networking opportunities. In this context, attendees will be in a rich atmosphere of information sharing and creating substantial change in hybrid sessions and presentations.
2. **Organizers:** The EduHeart Book Publishing in the Philippines, in coordination with the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University in Bangkok as conference organizer for the venue, will conduct the *Asian Multidisciplinary Research Conference (AMRC) 2025 in Bangkok, Thailand on Saturday, June 14, 2025*.
3. **Objectives:** The Asian Multidisciplinary Research Conference (AMRC) 2025 objectives are designed to foster collaboration, innovation, and knowledge exchange across disciplines. The key objectives include:
 - a. **Nurture Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** To provide a platform for researchers, educators, and professionals from diverse fields to share insights and work collaboratively on solving complex global challenges.
 - b. **Foster Knowledge Sharing:** To provide a forum where participants from throughout Asia and beyond may share leading-edge research findings, best practices, and innovative approaches.
 - c. **Advance Sustainable Solutions:** To explore strategies and solutions that will contribute to sustainable development, technological advancement, and the betterment of society.
 - d. **Support Emerging Scholars:** Empower early-career researchers, experts, and graduate students with a variety of opportunities for presentation, mentorship, and networking.
 - e. **Foster Global Networking:** To build relationships among participants across disciplines, institutions, and countries, with an eye toward future collaborations and partnerships.

f. Address Contemporary Challenges: Showcase multidisciplinary approaches to some of the most pressing challenges of our time, such as climate change, artificial intelligence, education, and technology-driven transformation.

These objectives reflect the conference’s commitment to advancing impactful research and fostering meaningful dialogue in a rapidly changing world.

4. **The Program:** The AMRC 2025 will be conducted in two forms:
 - a. *Preliminary program and the plenary speakers* will be held at the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand.
 - b. *The Breakout Session* will be done via onsite and via zoom.

ASIAN MULTIDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH CONFERENCE (AMRC) 2025		
Theme: Convergence of Knowledge: Influencing the Future through Multidisciplinary Approaches		
Time Duration	Activity	Remarks
8:00-9:00	Registration AVPs Event Safety Guidelines EduHeart Theme Song EduHeart Video Presentation	EduHeart Team Dr. Charlotte Yuson
9:00-9:30	Welcome Remarks	The President Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University Bangkok, Thailand
9:30-9:40	Opening Remarks Roll Call	Mr. Jerome N. Chua CEO, EduHeart Book Publishing
	Opening Cultural Numbers	SSRU Students Selected Filipino Students (<i>EAC Chorale</i>)
9:40-10:00	Keynote Speech <i>Convergence of Knowledge: Influencing the Future through Multidisciplinary Approaches</i>	Prof. Mario Pace Head of Department for Languages and Humanities Education University of Malta Malta (recorded presentation)
	Awarding of Certificate to Keynote Speaker Photo documentation	Host TWG

	Inspirational Speakers	<p>Dr. Elbert M. Galas University President Pangasinan State University Lingayen, Pangasinan, Philippines</p> <p>Dr. Rebecca D. Miranda Vice President for Academic Affairs Emilio Aguinaldo College – Cavite Dasmariñas, Cavite, Philippines</p> <p>Dr. Adrian Lawrence P. Carvajal Supervising Professional Regulations Officer, International Development Division, Professional Regulation Commission, Philippines</p> <p>Dr. Alfe M. Solina Chairperson, Management Department Cavite State University – Imus Campus Imus City, Cavite, Philippines</p>
	Awarding of Certificates to Inspirational Speakers Photo Documentation	<p>Host To be awarded by: Mr. Jerome N. Chua and Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua</p>
10:00-10:30	Plenary Speaker 1 The Role of Multidisciplinary Collaboration in Solving Global Challenges	<p>Napasri Suwanajote, Ph.D. Dean of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University Bangkok, Thailand</p>
	Awarding of Certificate to Plenary Speaker 1	<p>Host Mr. Jerome N. Chua Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua Dr. Alfe M. Solina</p>
10:30-11:00	Plenary Speaker 2 “ Motivation in Conducting Research ”	<p>Dr. Virginia Dulay-Akiate Former Regional Director, Commission on Higher Education Region IV-A, Philippines</p>
	Awarding of Certificate to Plenary Speaker 2	<p>Host Mr. Jerome N. Chua Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua Dr. Alfe M. Solina</p>
11:00-11:30	Plenary Speaker 3 “ Integrating AI Into Research ”	<p>Dr. Montarat Rungruangthum Research Consultant, Faculty of Liberal Arts, Rajamangala University of Technology Phra Nakhon, Thailand</p>

	Awarding of Certificate to Plenary Speaker 3	Host Mr. Jerome N. Chua Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua Dr. Alfe M. Solina
11:30-12:00	Plenary Speaker 4 “Bridging the Gap Between Academia, Industry, and Policy Making in TLE Research”	Dr. Rosalinda G. Cochico Chairperson, TVLE Pangasinan State University – Lingayen Campus, Lingayen Pangasinan, Philippines
	Awarding of Certificate to Plenary Speaker 4	Host Mr. Jerome N. Chua Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua Dr. Alfe M. Solina
	Surprise Number	Selected Students from Pangasinan State University – Philippines
12:00-1:15	Conference Reminders/Mechanics/etc. LUNCH BREAK	Host AVP
1:15-3:15	PARALLEL SESSIONS	SESSION CHAIR/MODERATOR FOR ON-SITE/ONLINE
	CLUSTER 1: EDUC/ TVLE HUMANITIES & SOCIAL SCIENCES	ON-SITE Session Chair Dr. Napasri Suwanajote Dr. Rosalinda G. Cochico Ms. Lilibeth S. Tiongson Moderator and Technical Support Dr. Ma. Glenda Mendoza ONLINE Session Chairs Dr. Phillip G. Queroda Dr. Amelita M. De Vera Dr. Ma. Christine Soroten Moderator Dr. Maria Virginia A. Fontanos Technical Support Ms. Melody A. Agustin
	CLUSTER 2: ENGR/ICT/ BUSINESS	ON-SITE Session Chair Dr. Priscila R. Castro Dr. Mellie Guico

		<p>Moderator and Technical Support Ms. Elaine Jairusse R. Capellan</p> <p>ONLINE Session Chairs</p> <p>Asst. Prof. Sixto N. Ras, Jr. Dr. Katherine V. Queroda Dr. Renato Salcedo Dr. Jessica James Paiso</p> <p>Moderator Ms. Mary Ann C. Soriano</p> <p>Technical Support Mr. Albert P. Ragasa</p>
	CLUSTER 3: STUDENT CATEGORY	<p>ON-SITE Session Chairs</p> <p>Dr. Roldan D. Atienza Dr. Agnes Arellano</p> <p>Moderator and Technical Support Dr. Isagani Y. Busito</p> <p>ONLINE Session Chairs</p> <p>Dr. Baby Karen Cristal Dr. Liane Vina G. Ocampo Asst. Prof. Maryann H. Lanuza</p> <p>Moderator Ms. Vladimir Marie E. Cabutotan</p> <p>Technical Support Ms. Noemi C. Orlanda</p>
3:15-3:30	<i>Consolidation of the results for Best Presenters</i> Intermission Number	Host and Technical Working Group Video Presentation
3:30-4:40	Book Launching Recognition of authors/editors/ et al.	Authors, Editors, and others To be awarded by: Dr. Jeth Chua and Mr. Jerome N. Chua

	Distribution of Certificates of Participation, Certificates of the Technical Working Group Announcement of Winners for Best Abstract, Best Paper, and Best Presenters	To award the certificates: Dr. Napasri Suwanajote Mr. Jerome N. Chua
4:40-4:50	Closing Remarks	Dr. Napasri Suwanajote Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand (<i>Conference Organizer</i>) Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua President, EduHeart Book Publishing
4:50-5:00	Photo documentation Evaluation* <i>with automatic cert of attendance</i>	All Participants All TWG Multimedia Presentation (<i>same day edit video</i>) Intermission number
<p><u>EduHeart Technical Working Group</u></p> <p><i>Program Hosts</i></p> <p>Mr. John Philip Alexander – onsite Ms. Marie Christine S. Pasco – onsite Mr. Charles Dustein Soriano – online</p>		

Mechanics of the Event

1. Participants in this conference may attend on-site or online. They may be graduate or undergraduate students, teachers, industry partners, administrators, or professionals from various fields.
2. The conference fees depend on the category of participants.

TYPE OF PARTICIPANTS	ONLINE	ONSITE
RESEARCH PRESENTER (GRADUATE STUDENTS/PROFESSIONALS)	USD 50	USD 100
CO-AUTHOR	USD 20	USD 50
OBSERVER/ATTENDEE (STUDENTS/GRADUATE STUDENTS/PROFESSIONALS)	USD 20	USD 50

3. The conference fee is inclusive of the following:
 - a. Conference Proceedings – hard copy –for Free and soft copy for online presenters
 - b. Certificate of Recognition as a presenter
 - c. Certificate of Publication – for those who wish to publish their work
 - d. Certificate of Participation and Attendance

- e. Certificate of Awards
- f. Snacks and Lunch

Note: All certificates will be printed for onsite participants only, and e-certificates for online participants.

4. **Publication:** EduHeart Book Publishing will provide titles of Scopus-Indexed Journals to which authors could possibly submit their papers at their own expense and upon the recommendation of the scientific committee. This is not part of the conference fee. The titles of the journals will be announced soon.

5. The Technical Working Group

CONFERENCE CHAIR: Dr. Ethel Reyes-Chua

CONFERENCE CO-CHAIRPERSONS: Dr. Alfe M. Solina (Cavite State University)
Dr. Ma. Leah P. Ulanday (Cavite State University – Silang Campus)

CONFERENCE VENUE ORGANIZERS: Dr. Napasri Suwanajote, Dr. Angvarrah Lieungnapar, Dr. Charlotte Yuson

COMMITTEE	ROLE	IN-CHARGE
Program and Invitation	<i>Invite participants from various colleges and universities.</i> <i>Create e-posters to be posted on social media.</i>	SSRU EduHeart
Proceedings	<i>Provide proceedings to all onsite participants.</i> <i>Compile all abstracts.</i>	EduHeart headed by Mr. Jerome N. Chua, Dr. Vladimir Marie E. Cabutotan
Physical Arrangements/Intermission numbers/pub mats, etc.	<i>Ensure that the venue is equipped with conference materials/equipment.</i> <i>Provide intermissions or cultural numbers for this event.</i> <i>Provide all the necessary publication materials for this event.</i> <i>Prepare one big room for Plenary Sessions, two rooms for breakout sessions, and for online and onsite.</i>	SSRU EduHeart

Scientific Committee	<p><i>Accept and review papers.</i></p> <p><i>Provide Notice of Acceptance and other communications.</i></p> <p><i>Send e-certificates to all participants.</i></p>	EduHeart and External Committee Technical Working Group
Technical Support	<p><i>Take charge of the technical aspects and assist the participants with their technical needs.</i></p> <p><i>Assist during the event.</i></p>	SSRU EduHeart headed by Mr. Wilson C. Bonifacio and all members of the Technical Support Group
Registration and Evaluation Committee (for online)	<p><i>Take charge of the online and onsite registration.</i></p> <p><i>Conduct a post-evaluation activity for all participants.</i></p>	EduHeart headed by Ms. Joice Pamela R. Zorca

6. **Script of the Event:** This will be taken care of by the assigned hosts, *John Philip and MC are for onsite support; Charles Dustein Soriano is for online support, with Mr. Bonifacio as onsite technical support and Mr. Albert Ragasa as online technical support.*

7. **Attire of the Technical Working Group:** **Opening: Filipiniana/Cultural**
Closing: Corporate
Attire of the Participants: Corporate

8. **Dry run:** The dry run will be conducted online a week before the event and F2F a day before.

9. **Specific Tasks and Timeline**

#	Task	DATE	SSRU	EDUHEART
1	Create e-poster	February 10, 2025		✓
2	Create a post on Facebook	February 14, 2025		✓
3	Share post on FB on CALL FOR PAPERS TO BE SENT VIA EMAIL OR GOOGLE FORM Call for attendees	February 14, 2025 to April 15, 2025		✓

4	Review all papers	As they come		✓
5	Send Notice of Acceptance	As they come		✓
6	Create the proceedings with ISSN Meetings online, etc.	April 2025		✓
7	Finalize papers for THE CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS (for those who are willing to submit their papers in the conference proceedings) Meetings online, etc.	April 2025		✓
8	Create all certificates Certificate of Participation Certificate of Recognition Certificate of Oral Presentation Best Paper and Best Abstract Awards Meetings online, etc.	May 2025	✓	✓
9	Finalize all tasks and activities Dry Run Meetings, etc.	1 st Week of June 2025		✓
10	Travel to Thailand (by 14 Philippine Delegates) Face-to-Face 1 st Meeting Formal Signing of MOU Dry Run Dinner with the SSRU	June 11, 2025 Wednesday	✓	✓

		June 12, 2025 (2 p.m.)		
11	Technical Support Team Meeting			
	The Conference Awarding of Certificates to SSRU and TWG	June 14, 2025 (Saturday)	✓	✓

Important Details:

1. The TWG will be in Thailand from June 11–16, 2025; June 16, 2025 – Travel to the Philippines.
2. The snacks and lunch shall be served to all VIPs, presenters, and TWG.
3. The venue organizer will be privileged to select at least 2-3 groups or participants for the conference, and EduHeart will conduct two free online training sessions for its faculty members.
4. Hard copies of the conference proceedings will be available for on-site participants only.
5. The conference will be held on two platforms:
 - a. ONSITE: There will be 3 clusters, which the participants and the assigned session chairs/moderators will attend.
 - b. ONLINE: There will be 3 clusters, to which the participants and assigned session chairs/moderators will attend via Zoom.
6. Live presentations will be conducted at the beginning of the plenary program and in the closing ceremony.
7. Changes to these details will be made depending on the situation.

ABSTRACT FORMAT

I. Abstract Outline:

- (1) Research Title
- (2) Name of researcher/affiliation, email address, mobile number
- (3) Abstract in IMRAD format
- (4) Five (5) Keywords

II. Full Paper Format:

The paper format includes the following:

- ✓ Abstract of 250 words
- ✓ Keywords (maximum of 5 words only)
- ✓ Introduction
- ✓ Methods
- ✓ Results and Discussion
- ✓ Conclusion/Recommendation
- ✓ References (APA, 7th edition format)

III. PowerPoint Presentations

SLIDES 1-2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● TITLE OF RESEARCH ● NAME ● AFFILIATION ● EMAIL ADDRESSES ● MOBILE NUMBER
SLIDES 3-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● INTRODUCTION ● BACKGROUND ● PROBLEM AREA/NEED OF RESEARCH ● RESEARCH METHODOLOGY
SLIDES 5-12	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● RESULTS AND DISCUSSION ● INTEGRATE CONCLUSIONS/RECOMMENDATIONS

IV. ABSTRACT GUIDELINES

INTRODUCTION AND IMPORTANCE

What is the problem, why are you researching, and why is this research necessary? Convince the readers that your research is significant and worthwhile to read. State a problem or explain why your present research is a timely and effective solution to the gap.

METHODS

What did you do to conduct your study? Explain what you did. Your intervention and how you did it!

RESULTS

The essence of your paper. How did you arrive at your results (methods) and their significance (introduction)? Explain and interpret your findings. Assess or evaluate the outcomes.

DISCUSSION

Summarize the main findings of the study. Connect these findings to other results findings. They discuss the flaws in the current study and use these flaws as reason to suggest additional information, future research make recommendations, etc.

ORAL PRESENTATION GUIDELINES

V. CRITERIA

A. BEST ABSTRACT

Significance of the Topic/Issue to the field of Research	60%
A. Importance of the Issue to the field of research	20%
B. Value of writing and other elements	20%
C. Conceptual Consistency of writing (objectives/argument)	20%
Methods Used	10%
Relevance and Practicality of Results/Discussion/Conclusion	20%
Paper's Contribution to Research/Institution/Community	10%
TOTAL	100%

B. BEST PRESENTER

Presentation Strategy	30%
Delivery and Confidence	30%
Materials to capture the audience's attention	20%
Ability to Answer Questions	20%
TOTAL	100%

C. BEST PAPER

1. Significance of the Topic/Issue to the field of Research	60%
Importance of the Issue to the field of research	10%
Value of writing and other elements	10%
Conceptual Consistency of writing (objectives/argument)	10%
Methodological Consistency (design/sampling/data collection)	10%
General discussion and Conclusion	10%
Paper's Contribution to research/institution	10%
2. Manuscript (Creativity/Originality/Quality of Work)	40%
TOTAL	100%

The Abstracts

Development and Content Validity of the Book: Environmental Disaster, Sanitation, and Waste Management

Analyn I. Diola

*Lyceum Northwestern University
Philippines*

ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the content validity, readability, and curriculum alignment of educational materials focused on environmental disasters, sanitation, and waste management. Expert assessments used the Item-Level Content Validity Index (I-CVI) and Scale-Level Content Validity Index (S-CVI) to confirm high validity across all indicators, with I-CVI scores ranging from 0.929 to 0.986. Teacher evaluations consistently achieved perfect validity scores, reinforcing the material's strong alignment with curricular objectives. The study also established a significant positive correlation between curriculum alignment and both content accuracy ($\rho = .943, p = .000$) and readability ($\rho = .894, p = .000$), underscoring the importance of structured, logically sequenced instructional materials in facilitating student comprehension. Additionally, significant differences in teacher and student perceptions revealed the need for a balanced approach to educational resource development, integrating expert validation with student feedback. The findings highlight the necessity of periodic content updates, readability assessments, and collaborative curriculum development to ensure educational materials remain accurate, relevant, and engaging.

Keywords: *Curriculum Alignment, Content Validity, Readability Assessment, Educational Materials, Environmental Education*

Plant-Based Diets and its Impacts on Metabolic Syndrome: A Rapid Review

Joana L. Yasol-Vicente¹ and Bethlehem P. Maloles²

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ABSTRACT

Background. Metabolic syndrome is a cluster of conditions that increases the risk of cardiovascular disease and diabetes. Plant-based diets may have beneficial effects on metabolic syndrome which include abdominal obesity, high blood pressure, high blood sugar, high triglycerides, and low HDL cholesterol. The aim of this study was to provide a rapid review of the current evidence on the effects of plant-based diets on metabolic syndrome, based on the results of observational and intervention studies. Methods. A literature search was conducted at a single point in time in December 2023 utilizing the Scopus electronic database to identify potentially relevant studies and publications for inclusion. A total of 112 articles retrieved from Scopus underwent screening for inclusion in the literature search. The search strategy involved the development of a combination of keywords and medical subject heading terms associated with plants and metabolic syndrome. Results. Eleven (11) articles met the inclusion criteria. Most of the studies, however, indicated a potential causal link between a healthful plant-based diet and a decreased risk of metabolic syndrome (particularly in relation to abdominal obesity). The findings of the study indicated that following a nutritious plant dietary diet was linked to increased HDL cholesterol and decreased weight in MetS patients. Conclusion. In conclusion, following a nutritious plant-based diet was linked to increased HDL cholesterol and decreased weight in MetS patients.

Keywords: *metabolic syndrome, plant-based diet, vegan, vegetarian, obesity, weight loss*

Cultural Institutions and Policy Implementation in Pangasinan: A Study on the Role of Local Museums and Heritage Sites

Dr. Adrian Lawrence P. Carvajal¹ and Dr. Teddy M. Fernandez²

¹Professional Regulation Commission

²Pangasinan State University

ABSTRACT

This study will examine the role of cultural institutions in preserving local heritage in Pangasinan and will analyze how government policies support the implementation of cultural programs in the region. Specifically, the research will explore the contributions of museums and heritage sites in promoting historical awareness, cultural identity, and tourism development. Using a case study approach, the study will collect qualitative and quantitative data through interviews with museum employees and heritage site staff, as well as survey responses from visitors to these institutions. The findings will assess the effectiveness of existing cultural policies and will identify challenges related to policy enforcement, funding, and public engagement. The results will provide recommendations for strengthening government support for cultural institutions, enhancing heritage preservation efforts, and increasing community involvement in cultural initiatives.

Keywords: *cultural institutions, heritage preservation, museum policies, government support, Pangasinan, cultural policy analysis*

Grammar Proficiency of English Major Students In Pangasinan State University, Asingan Campus

Joross M. Salapungol
Pangasinan State University

ABSTRACT

This study explored the grammar proficiency of English major students at Pangasinan State University, Asingan Campus. It examined its relationship with selected profile variables such as sex, age, year level, preferred grammar assistance, and grammar-checking tools or applications. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, and a researcher-made grammar test was used to measure the students' skills in vocabulary, grammar accuracy, and sentence structure. The gathered data were analyzed using Pearson correlation. Results revealed that all profile variables showed negligible relationships with grammar proficiency, suggesting that these factors, whether demographic or technological, had no significant influence on the students' grammar skills. Despite the increasing availability of grammar assistance tools, the findings imply that adequate grammar mastery may rely more on direct instruction and practice. In response to these findings, an innovative work plan was developed to address the gaps in grammar proficiency. This plan offers targeted learning activities, interactive sessions, and student-centered strategies to improve grammar performance regardless of students' backgrounds or tool preferences.

Proposing a Competency Management and Professional Development Plan to Enhance the Competency Levels of Senior High School TVL Teachers: A Case Study in SDO1 Pangasinan

Dr. Rosalinda G. Cochico
Pangasinan State University

ABSTRACT

This qualitative research sought to build a competence management and professional development strategy to elevate the competency levels of Senior High School Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) instructors in SDO1 Pangasinan. The research employed a case study methodology, collecting data via comprehensive interviews and focus group talks with TVL educators, administrators, and industry stakeholders. The results identified numerous critical elements affecting the competency levels of TVL teachers, such as their educational background, professional experience, and availability of continuous training opportunities. Numerous educators expressed concerns of inadequacy regarding their competences, mostly attributed to restricted professional development opportunities and the swiftly changing requirements of the vocational education sector. The proposed competency management strategy highlighted the necessity for a systematic framework that links professional development programs with instructors' specialized skills and the abilities demanded by the industry. The plan included tactics including regular needs assessments, customized training programs, and mentorship opportunities to promote ongoing growth and adaptation. The study emphasized the significance of a comprehensive approach to teacher development, which promotes individual capabilities and eventually improves student results in TVL programs, by promoting collaboration between educational institutions and business partners. This research advanced the discourse on teacher professional development in the Philippines, providing pragmatic recommendations for policymakers and educational leaders to enhance the quality of vocational education.

Keywords: Professional development strategy, competency level, TVL teachers, training opportunities, teacher development

The National Security Council Towards a Strategic Lasting West Philippine Sea International Relationship

Gilmore M. Rioveros, PhD

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ABSTRACT

This paper examined the National Security Council (NSC)'s strategic dynamics in affecting long-term West Philippine Sea relations. The examination will examine how geopolitics, marine security, and international law affect national security. This study examines how defensive technology advances and strategic alliances affect regional diplomacy. It also assessed the socio-economic effects of territorial conflicts, resource access, and regional stability at local and global levels. The study utilized the qualitative approach and it conducted Focus Group Discussion in order to find out the perspectives of the concerned high ranking officials regarding the international relations in general and focus on ASEAN, the US, and China. The study found out that the national security decisions affect defense, security, and trade. This study recommends a creation of the West Philippine Sea policy framework that fosters collaboration and ensures long-term security. The study recommends to further strengthen the National Security's Council Participation in policy formation for the West Philippine Seas (WPS) and to improve the NSC's capability for proactive engagement and resource mobilization. Finally, the study recommends further study of this research to emphasize the formulation of extensive educational and awareness initiatives on WPS policies, significance of national sovereignty and international collaboration.

Keywords: National Security, West Philippine Seas, Defense, Trade, International Collaboration

Development of Worksheets and Templates for Research and Level of Acceptability among Research Students of PSU - Asingan Campus

Diola, Analyn I., Corpuz, Ermalique S. and Castillo, Carlos Jr. G.
Pangasinan State University

ABSTRACT

Conducting and designing the research project is a common bottleneck among college graduates. Research manuscript writing is also one of the difficulties commonly encountered by students. Teacher-researchers developed and enhanced worksheets and templates to facilitate the research experiences of the student-respondents. The worksheets were used in Technology and Livelihood Education Research and Industrial Technology Product Design and Development classes. The Worksheets and Templates were evaluated in terms of clarity and content. Also, acceptability of the Worksheets and Templates was measured in terms of advantages, disadvantages, difficulties, and overall emotional insight into the Worksheets. As a result, the Worksheets were excellent in clarity and content. The worksheets and templates provided facilitated the writing of the manuscript and gave ample time for the student-researchers on product development. However, some of the terms used were difficult for the students. The study also revealed a need to evaluate the learning materials, such as worksheets and Templates, to ensure clarity, accuracy, appropriateness, and up-to-dateness. Overall, the students were happy and had positive impressions towards the Worksheets and Templates.

Keywords: *Research Worksheet and Templates, Technology and Livelihood Education Research, Industrial Technology Product Design and Development*

Teaching Strategies in the Elementary Grades

Dr. John Rey V. Bautista

Francisco E. Barzaga Memorial School

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study explored effective teaching strategies in the elementary grades, focusing on how various approaches influence student engagement, understanding, and academic performance. The research investigated five key areas: student-centered and active learning approaches, differentiated instruction, using visuals and multisensory tools, technology integration, and the impact of formative assessment with constructive feedback. Findings revealed through thematic and documentary analysis that student-centered and active learning strategies, such as collaborative group work and inquiry-based activities, significantly enhanced young learners' engagement and critical thinking skills. Differentiated instruction effectively addressed the diverse learning needs of students by tailoring content and processes to individual abilities and preferences. The study also found that incorporating visuals, manipulatives, and multisensory tools promoted deeper conceptual understanding and retention, particularly in mathematics and literacy. Furthermore, purposeful technology integration, including educational apps and interactive platforms, supported personalized learning pathways and provided real-time feedback, fostering independent study habits. Lastly, formative assessments coupled with constructive feedback played a vital role in tracking student progress and boosting motivation by helping learners recognize their strengths and areas for growth. Overall, the study underscored the importance of employing various evidence-based teaching strategies to create an inclusive, engaging, and effective elementary classroom environment. Recommendations emphasized the need for continuous professional development for educators, the provision of diverse learning materials, and the thoughtful integration of technology and assessment practices to support all learners' academic success.

Keywords: *Elementary education, teaching strategies, student engagement, differentiated instruction, formative assessment*

React, Share, Educate: A Mixed Methods Study on Facebook Content Impact in a Philippine Secondary School

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ABSTRACT

The Department of Education – General Santos City Division created the DepEd Tayo GenSan Facebook (DTG FB) Page where news, feature stories, advocacy videos, and announcements were posted for public awareness; however, such an initiative faced several issues and concerns, including the observed decreasing viewers' engagement to its contents. Moreover, the aforementioned initiative needed assessment and evaluation due to its novelty. Furthermore, not much was known about government social media pages as proven by the dearth of literature. Thus, the said issues and gaps necessitated a profound investigation. A survey was conducted to randomly selected teachers, master teachers, and school heads (N=651) and Focus Group Discussion to the purposively identified DepEd GenSan personnel (N=9). It determined the extent of their engagement, level of satisfaction, and experiences vis-à-vis DTG FB Page contents in the New Normal. It employed the explanatory-sequential mixed methods design, combining quantitative (descriptive-correlation) and qualitative (case study) approaches. The study's findings revealed that the DepEd personnel's engagement was associated with their satisfaction level. Further, the DepEd personnel experienced being informed, participating actively, discovering passion, and getting inspired when engaging to DTG FB Page. The satisfaction was due to the quality content on the DTG FB Page, the ability of the said platform to answer queries, and the satisfactory time duration of videos. Resultantly, the Division Communication Enhancement Plan and the advocacy video were crafted as contextualized strategies for improved public engagement and satisfaction.

Keywords - DepEd Tayo GenSan Facebook Page, engagement, satisfaction, DepEd Personnel, Mixed Methods Approach

Evaluating Awareness and Compliance with Osh Standards in the Philippine Construction Industry: Insights for Safer Workplaces

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ABSTRACT

This study examined awareness and compliance to occupational safety and health (OSH) standards among contractors and construction workers in the 2nd Congressional District of Negros Oriental for the year 2023. The research indicates that although employees demonstrate a good comprehension of occupational safety and health rules, risk assessment, and safety protocols, substantial deficiencies persist in recording of risk assessments and emergency response training. A correlation analysis demonstrated a robust association between awareness levels and compliance, highlighting the necessity for improved training programs. The study indicates that addressing highlighted problems, particularly in hazard communication and personal protective equipment utilization, is vital for fostering a safer building workplace. Recommendations encompass the formulation of extensive training techniques, the implementation of frequent safety drills, and the establishment of continuous feedback mechanisms to enhance learning and ensure compliance with OSH requirements.

Keywords: occupational safety and health standards, construction, awareness and compliance.

Predictors of Performance in The Licensure Examination for the Bachelor of Elementary Graduates of PSU-Alaminos City Campus

Jocelyn Sagun-De Vera, PhD.

College of Teacher Education

Elementary and General Education Department

Pangasinan State University, Alaminos City Campus

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the factors affecting the licensure examination performance of Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) 2021-2022 graduates from the College of Teacher Education at Pangasinan State University, Alaminos City Campus. The study involves 51 (44 female, 7 males) who passed the August 2023 LET Exam of the Bachelor of Elementary Education. A descriptive correlational research design, in which the graduates' academic performance and other factors that significantly predicted their LET performance were examined, particularly on a.) LET performance of the graduates in professional and general education across profile variables b.) the significant relationship of LET performance across profile variables. c.) significant predictors of BEED LET performance among the considered predictors (profile) variables. Through the use of Facebook Messenger and emails, the passers were forwarded a survey form. Results showed that sex is significantly related to BEEd graduates' LET performance as signified by the significance value of .041, which is less than the significance level of $\alpha=0.05$. Female BEEd graduates tend to have better performance in LET than of male graduates. Also, attendance at LET review is positively and strongly related to BEEd graduates' LET performance ($r=.797$; $p<0.05$). Lastly, the college GPA of BEEd graduates is significantly related to their LET performance. Particularly, higher college GPA or academic performance would result in a better performance of BEEd graduates in LET.

Keywords: *LET performance, predictors, review, awardee, graduates*

Thes-Is It Girlies: The Empowering Impact of Social Media Trends on the Feminist Consciousness of Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences Students

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ABSTRACT

Modern feminism has evolved and expanded its reach of awareness through several mediums—including the digital world. Sequentially, social media as a network of activism-related platforms has played significant roles for feminism in the digital world. Previous studies have proven that despite such advancements, women still experience extreme poverty, unfair wage, sexual abuse, physical violence, and lack of freedom (United Nations Women, 2025). Through this study, the position of feminism in the digital lens was challenged by analysis through correlational research design and simple random sampling for its respondents. The participants were Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences students in Emilio Aguinaldo College Cavite where 123 responded. With the use of Google Survey Forms in Likert Scale, the researchers were able to collect the responses and analyze it through the Pearson's R statistical test. The obtained data comprised grand means that were closely correlated, with variable 1 (social media trends) and variable 2 (feminist consciousness) having 4.98 and 5.22, respectively. Upon conducting Pearson-R analysis, they obtained a value of one (1)—signifying a perfect positive correlation between the two variables. Given these findings, the researchers concluded that the amount of exposure to social media trends affects the consciousness of Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences students on feminism. This supports the claim of Agojo et al. (2023) that social media continues to evolve as a powerful platform for feminist activism. In response, the researchers proposed an advocacy project titled “HERStory Digitally” to apply these findings into a community-based initiative.

Keywords: *Correlational Study, Feminism, Social Media Trends, Feminist Consciousness, Social Media Platforms*

Stakeholders' Engagements in School-Based Management Initiatives: Basis for Strategic Plan

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ABSTRACT

Stakeholder engagement is essential for the effective implementation of school-based management initiatives. This study explores the level of stakeholder participation in educational governance in Pinamalayan West District, Oriental Mindoro, and examines the factors influencing their involvement. Using a descriptive-correlational research design, the study analyzed the demographic profiles of stakeholders, their engagement in decision-making, resource contribution, and school activities, as well as the challenges they encounter.

Findings indicate that stakeholders exhibit a moderate level of participation, with engagement influenced by factors such as age, position, and training attendance. Key challenges include financial constraints, limited institutional support, and resistance to change. To enhance stakeholder involvement, a strategic plan is proposed, focusing on improved communication, capacity-building programs, collaboration initiatives, and incentive mechanisms. Strengthening stakeholder engagement is expected to foster more inclusive and effective school-based management, ultimately improving educational outcomes in the district.

Keywords: *stakeholder engagement, school-based management, educational governance, strategic plan*

Unveiling the Style of Columnists in Expressing their Views on Contemporary Issues in Education

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ABSTRACT

Education columnists are generally known for expressing their views on various education-related issues and for advocating for reforms in certain areas. These types of journalists are found across both print and online forms of major newspapers, especially major broadsheets. Ramos' and Genuino's study focuses on selected education columnists' styles, particularly focusing on the use of two major types of modals (epistemic and deontic) and on the reasons behind the prevalence of certain modals, with Modality Theory by Halliday as the main framework. Using document analysis, the authors examined contemporary column articles from two major educators/columnists: Pia Roces Morato and Eleanor Pinugu, and determined the categories to which the modals belonged according to function and intention. The results of the study generally revealed that epistemic modals were more frequently used than deontic modals. Several possible reasons cited were the authors' desire to inform rather than impose and that the authors adopted a more recommendatory tone rather than an imperative one, most notably when suggesting solutions for education-related problems. It is recommended that other types of modals be examined throughout Filipino education columnists' articles and that comparative analyses of modal use be conducted in light of stylistic analysis.

Gaging Experience in Using Digital Payments Among Filipino People Researchers

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ABSTRACT

Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas announced that the share of digital payment transactions to total monthly retail payments in the Philippines grew from 42.1 percent in 2022 to 52.8 percent, according to the 2023 Report on E-Payments Measurement on the Bangko Sentral ng Pilipinas. This indicates that the central bank has surpassed its target of digitalizing 50 percent of digital payments volume in the country under its Digital Payments Transformation Roadmap 2018 – 2023.

This study seeks to measure the experience of Filipinos in using digital payments by (1) determining the demographic profile of participants; (2) identifying the level of assessment of Filipino people using digital payments; (3) determine the challenges encountered while using digital payments; (4) examine the sentiments of Filipino people on using digital technology like digital payments based on their experience; (5) examine the significant relationship between the level of assessment of Filipino people using digital payments and the challenges being encountered; and (6) examine the significant difference between the level of assessment of Filipino people based on their experience when grouped according to their education.

This study is a mixed-method research design using descriptive and correlational analysis. The researchers used frequency and percentage, mean and standard deviation, Spearman's Rank Correlation, Kruskal-Wallis, and Thematic Analysis using Coding Method. Data was gathered using surveys from 115 digital payment users through a random sampling method

The study revealed that 60% of the digital payment users are Gen. Z. G-Cash is the most prevalent among the digital payment systems, with 105 out of 115, with 91.30 %, users. Findings assessed that "Speed" in using digital payment is the best factor why Filipinos use it, and "Security Concerns" is the first concern of customers regarding the privacy of their transactions. Findings suggest that "transaction fees" have a meaningful impact on the system's reliability. Key findings emphasize that "security concerns" are shared relatively equally among all users, regardless of their educational background.

The researchers present valuable recommendations to the government, LGU's, digital payment systems providers, and users of digital payment systems to strengthen the laws on providing a secure digital payment system experience, utilizing a widespread of digital payment system know-how through printed forms, media, websites, apps, and enhancing security features, implementing a reliable, fast, accessible, trusted and minimal transactions fees that are available to all users of digital payment system.

Keywords: *Digital Payments, Digital Technology, Digital Financial Inclusion, 13 SDG Goals on Digital Payment System, Gaging the Filipinos' Level of Assessment on Using Digital Payments, Gaging Filipinos' Challenges on Using Digital Payments.*

Lab Matters: Experiences of Grade 7 Science Learners and Science Teachers in Experiential Learning

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the experiences of Grade 7 learners and their science teachers in the context of experiential learning. Utilizing phenomenological analysis, the research examined how hands-on activities impact learners' comprehension, engagement, and emotional responses. Findings reveal that experiential learning fosters deeper understanding of scientific concepts, enhances student motivation, and promotes active participation. Learners reported positive emotions, such as excitement and curiosity, which increased their interest and retention. However, challenges emerged, including anxiety over first-time experiments and the need for structured support. Teachers identified barriers such as limited resources, classroom management issues, and time constraints but emphasized the effectiveness of hands-on learning in bridging theory and practice. Both learners and teachers highlighted the importance of clear instructions, guidance, and sufficient resources in facilitating successful experiential learning. The study proposes the D.O.I.N.G. framework, which emphasizes curiosity, inquiry, reflection, collaboration, and real-world applications to address these challenges and optimize experiential learning outcomes. This research underscores the transformative power of experiential learning in making science education more engaging and accessible while identifying critical areas for improvement to ensure its successful implementation.

Keywords: *Experiential learning, Grade 7 learners, science education, hands-on activities, learner engagement, D.O.I.N.G. framework, phenomenological analysis*

Enhancing Employee Motivation and Job Satisfaction: A Study of Government-Owned and Controlled Corporations

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ABSTRACT

Employee motivation and job satisfaction are critical factors influencing the productivity and well-being of employees in government-owned and controlled corporations. Despite their importance, little is known about how motivation and job satisfaction interrelate in such institutions. This study sought to explore the level of motivation and job satisfaction among employees of the SSS, GSIS, and Pag-IBIG in Cebu City and Mandaue City. A quantitative-descriptive method was employed, utilizing both online and face-to-face questionnaires for data collection. Convenience and quota sampling techniques were used to select 300 participants from the three corporations. The findings revealed that employees exhibited high levels of motivation in terms of achievement and affiliation, and satisfactory levels of job satisfaction regarding working relationships. Additionally, a significant positive relationship was found between motivation and job satisfaction, manifesting that higher levels of motivation correlate with increased job satisfaction. Based on these findings, the management may implement recognition programs, rewards, and incentives to enhance employee motivation. Furthermore, improving office processes and creating clear career progression opportunities contribute to a more motivated and satisfied workforce.

Keywords: *Employee Motivation, Job Satisfaction, Government-Owned Corporations, SSS, GSIS, Pag-IBIG*

Examining City Ordinance No. 3, Series of 2019: A Policy Analysis on Impact, Challenges, and Strategies

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ABSTRACT

This research delves into the impact of local ordinances on addressing juvenile delinquency, explicitly evaluating the effectiveness of Ordinance No. 3, Series of 2019, in General Santos City. The primary aim is to assess how this ordinance reduces the number of Children in Conflict with the Law (CICL) in the city. The study relies on primary data collected through face-to-face interviews conducted in the twenty-six (26) barangays of General Santos City. It centers on the respondents' responses during these interviews, supplemented by reviewing published articles, research studies, and laws relevant to the subject matter. The study investigates collaborative efforts among community stakeholders and evaluates the enforcement mechanisms. The findings will offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of local ordinances as customized interventions for CICL, providing recommendations for refining and optimizing such legal frameworks to better cater to the unique needs of communities and the children within them.

Keywords: Policy Analysis, City Ordinance No. 3 Series of. 2019, Children in Conflict with the Law, Juvenile Justice Welfare Act, General Santos City

Exploring the Influence of Gamification on Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes in Mathematics Classrooms for Grades K-12

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study was undertaken in mathematics classrooms in the Philippines to investigate the impact of gamification on student engagement and learning outcomes. The study uncovered significant and profound effects that occurred as a result of incorporating gamified learning exercises. Increased student engagement was seen when mathematics lessons were augmented with gamification components such as points, badges, and leaderboards, leading to heightened interest and participation. Furthermore, the implementation of gamification greatly enhanced students' motivation in the field of mathematics by offering explicit goals and rewards that stimulated active engagement and persistence in problem-solving activities. The implementation of gamification in mathematics education enhanced students' learning interest by making topics more accessible and relatable. This, in turn, fostered a positive peer influence and facilitated a collaborative learning environment. In addition, gamification enabled the provision of personalized learning experiences that addressed the specific requirements and preferences of individual students, thereby improving concentration and fostering positive attitudes towards mathematical challenges. These studies highlight the effectiveness of gamification in improving student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes in mathematics education in various educational contexts in the Philippines.

Keywords: *Gamification, student engagement, learning outcomes, students' motivation, personalized learning experiences*

Framework in Designing a Contextualized – Localized Instructional Materials in Mathematics for Technical Vocational Livelihood Senior High School Students

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to develop a framework for designing contextualized and localized instructional materials in Mathematics for Technical-Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Senior High School students. The primary goal was to enhance the relevance and effectiveness of mathematics education by aligning instructional content with the needs of students, the business and industry sectors, and both national and international educational standards. This alignment is critical in promoting mathematical literacy and equipping learners with essential 21st-century skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and real-world application.

To realize the objectives of the study, a descriptive research design was employed, specifically utilizing a descriptive-survey method to assess the acceptability of the proposed framework. The development process followed the ADDIE model (Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, Evaluation), ensuring a structured approach aligned with DepEd standards, international large-scale assessments, and industry-specific competencies. Data were collected through surveys and interviews with TVL teachers, curriculum planners, and representatives from the business sector within the Division of City Schools Manila.

The findings highlighted the support of different stakeholders for the framework, particularly its emphasis on contextualization, localization, and alignment with real-world industry demands. The framework effectively integrated authentic problem-solving tasks and real-life scenarios designed to enhance students' mathematical literacy and workplace readiness. Statistical analyses including descriptive statistics, ANOVA, and the Kruskal-Wallis Test revealed no significant differences among stakeholder responses, indicating a high level of consensus regarding the framework's relevance, quality, and practical utility.

Based on the results, it is recommended that teachers, curriculum developers, and industry professionals collaborate in the implementation of the framework in TVL mathematics education. A sample prototype instructional material should be developed to support this initiative and demonstrate practical application. Educators are strongly encouraged to adopt the framework as a model for designing instructional content that is responsive to both industry demands and international education frameworks, ultimately fostering globally competitive and mathematically literate graduates. Future research should consider expanding the application of this framework to other academic domains and continuously evaluate its relevance in light of evolving educational and workforce trends.

Keywords: contextualization and localization, framework, ADDIE Model, descriptive statistics

Mga Mungkahing Gabay Estratehiya sa Pagtuturo ng Maikling Kuwento at Nobela na Nagwagi sa Carlos Palanca

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ABSTRAK

Lagom

Mayaman sa akdang-pampanitikan ang mga Pilipino na kung saan nakalahad ang kanilang mga damdamin, suliranin at pananaw. Hindi maitatanggi ang malaking kontribusyon nito sa kasaysayan ng bansa sapagkat dito makikita kung ano ang buhay ng mga tao noon. Naipakikita sa panitikan ang iba't ibang pananaw na nalikha ng tao kagaya ng kung paano siya mag-isip ng mga bagay-bagay, kung paano siya magpahalaga at kumilala sa kapwa tao at sa tradisyon na kaniyang ginagawa sa araw-araw niyang buhay sa mundong ginagalawan. Ang panitikan ay naipapahayag sa paraang pasalita at pasulat ng mga damdaming Pilipino hinggil sa kanilang pamumuhay, paniniwala, pamahalaan, lipunan, kaisipan, pamahiin, pananampalataya at karanasan na hinahabi sa isang maganda at masining na paraan.

Subalit hindi maikakaila ang bilang ng mga mag-aaral na walang interes sa pagkatuto sa Filipino, lalong lalo na sa Panitikan. Para sa isang guro, ang pagtuturo nito ay isang gawaing hindi madali; ito ay nangangailangan ng mga estratehiya at kagamitan upang maging maganda ang daloy ng talakayan sa loob ng klase. Kinakailangang gawing interaktibo at integratibo ang talakayan sa loob ng klase upang alisin ang pagkabagot ng mag-aaral sa pag-aaral nito. Kaya naman isang hamon sa isang guro kung paano makukuha ang atensyon ng kanyang mag-aaral, kung paano magagawang kawili-wili ang panitikan sa pagtuturo at talakayan sa loob ng klase, kung paano maituturo sa mga mag-aaral ang kahalagahan ng panitikan, at kung paano ito maisasalin hanggang sa susunod na henerasyon.

Nakasentro ang pag-aaral sa pagbuo ng mga mungkahing gabay estratehiya sa pagtuturo ng maikling kuwento at nobela. Ito ay naglalayong alamin ang tema ng mga kuwento at nobela, katangian ng manunulat, elemento ng akda, literary devices at dulong pampanitikan na lumutang sa akdang sinuri.

Readiness in Research Writing: Bases for Preparation of a Learning Package

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the extent of students' manifestation of research competencies—specifically in problem identification, literature review, and research methodology—and its relationship to their readiness for thesis writing in terms of writing skills, access to resources, and awareness of research methods. Additionally, it explored the challenges students encountered in research writing. A quantitative descriptive research design was utilized, employing a survey questionnaire to gather data on the self-perceived research readiness of third-year students. Stratified random sampling was used to select 337 respondents from Batangas State University-TNEU Pablo Borbon Main Campus. Data were analyzed using composite mean, weighted mean, and Pearson's Correlation. The results showed that students demonstrated a manifested level of research competencies, indicating a solid foundation in problem identification, literature review, and research methodology. However, their readiness for thesis writing in terms of writing skills, access to resources, and awareness of research methods was rated as moderately prepared. A significant relationship was found between the extent of research competencies and students' thesis writing readiness. Students reported facing several challenges in research writing, including difficulties in developing a comprehensive research framework, operationalizing key terms, and ensuring a representative sample. These findings suggest a need for targeted interventions to strengthen students' research skills. To address these challenges and enhance readiness, the study proposes a learning package in the form of a handbook containing structured activities. This package serves as a comprehensive guide designed to support students through the research writing process by offering clear instructions, expectations, and tools for academic success.

Keywords: *research writing, research competencies, writing skills, readiness and learning package.*

Reserve Officer Training Course: Shaping Students' Life Skills and Resiliency Towards Nation Building

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ABSTRACT

Enhancing civic consciousness and defense preparedness including resiliency in times of disaster or situation that test the strength of a country is part of the program of the Philippine Government. In accordance with the mandate of Republic Act No. 9163 known as National Service Training Program act of 2001, one of the components is the Reserve Officers' Training Course (ROTC). The program's outcomes were evaluated to determine whether it is responsive to the needs of the national government and local communities. It utilized the descriptive research design, along with a researcher-made survey questionnaire administered to 121 respondents, comprising ROTC graduates who are already employed in different fields and 63 fourth year students from colleges in Region IV-A (CALABARZON). Findings revealed that the ROTC program was most focused on preparing students for challenges related to insurgency and national security threats and in fostering patriotism, despite some identified weaknesses, the program has equipped students in handling emergencies and disasters. However, the most significant weaknesses identified are the needs of the students with essential life-saving skills that will prepare them for various disaster scenarios, and focus on comprehensive and practical training. A review of the ROTC Program of Instructions, as well as improvements in training and instruction delivery, will assist in fulfilling national mandates and in shaping the future towards a national long-term vision of the Philippines where families thrive in vibrant, culturally diverse, and resilient communities.

Keywords: *Life-saving skills, behavioral improvement, disaster preparedness, insurgencies, advantages, weaknesses*

Pre-Service Teachers' Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (Tpack): Application of Learning in Teaching Internship

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the pre-service teachers' application of Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK) competencies and their relationship to teaching internship performance. Technology integration in education enhances teaching and learning, and TPACK provides a framework for understanding the interaction between technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge.

A descriptive-correlational design was used, involving 227 pre-service teachers from a state university in Batangas. Data were collected through a survey questionnaire covering technological, pedagogical, and content knowledge, as well as their integration. Findings revealed that pre-service teachers demonstrated strong competencies across all TPACK domains, suggesting a solid foundation for integrating technology into their teaching. Their teaching internship performance reflected the successful application of TPACK principles in real-world classroom settings.

Furthermore, results indicated a positive relationship between TPACK scores and teaching performance, implying that higher TPACK competency enhances teaching effectiveness with digital technologies. This underscores the significance of TPACK in pre-service teacher education and highlights the need for equipping future educators with essential technological integration skills.

Keywords: *Pre-service teachers, TPACK, Teaching Internship, Teaching Performance.*

Integration of Sustainable Development Goals Targets in the Teaching of General Education Courses

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the extent of integration of Sustainable Development Goals targets in teaching General Education courses. This study assessed students' engagement level in observing sustainability practices and policies, and examined the relationship between the extent of integration of sustainable development goals targets and the students' engagement in observing sustainability practices and policies. The researchers prepared learning activities that will maintain the integration of SDG targets in general education courses. Descriptive-correlational design was used to gather useful information to achieve the objectives of the study. Two hundred ninety-one students from the College of Teacher Education were identified using a stratified sampling technique. The data gathering instrument used was a survey questionnaire, and well distributed to the respondents. Weighted mean and Pearson's r product correlation were used in treating the statistical data. The findings revealed that the teachers integrate sustainable development goals targets in teaching General Education courses in learning activities, instructions, and assessment of learning to a moderate extent. The study also revealed that students are moderately engaged in observing sustainability practices and policies. Thus, the statistical correlation also indicated that the null hypothesis was rejected, hence extent of integration of SDGs targets and the level of engagement in observing sustainability practices and policies were significantly related. Based on the findings, learning activities integrating sustainable development goals targets in General Education courses were prepared by the researchers, in the classroom learning activities, done by the students, as per the instructions of their subject teachers.

Keywords: *Sustainable development goals, general education courses, learning activities, instructions, and assessment of learning*

Reconceptualizing ICT Proficiency: Strategic Upskilling of TLE Educators in the Digital Age

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ABSTRACT

This study seeks to reconceptualize ICT proficiency by developing a strategic lesson exemplar aimed at upskilling Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) secondary teachers in the digital era. Targeting 264 educators in the Division of Batangas Province, the research assessed their ICT competencies across four domains: technological operations and concepts, social and ethical responsibility, pedagogical integration, and professional application. It also examined how these competencies are manifested in teaching practices—specifically in content delivery, pedagogy, assessment and reporting, as well as personal and professional growth.

A strong positive correlation was found between the teachers' level of ICT skills and their degree of application in classroom instruction. While the overall proficiency and application levels were found to be high, challenges—particularly slow internet connectivity—were identified as significant barriers to effective ICT integration.

The resulting lesson exemplar is strategically crafted with clear objectives, interactive activities, and targeted outputs to reinforce and expand the ICT capabilities of TLE educators. Ultimately, this study supports a transformative approach to ICT training, promoting continuous professional development in response to the evolving demands of digital teaching and learning.

Keywords: *ICT Proficiency, Strategic Upskilling, Digital Teaching, TLE Educators, Batangas Province*

Reinforcing Stakeholders' Engagement to Sustainability Practices

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ABSTRACT

The study assessed the stakeholders' engagement to sustainability practices. It described the Batangas State University stakeholders in terms of age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, academic rank, and designation. It also determined the extent of engagement relative to curriculum and teaching methods, policies and initiatives, sustainable university operations, and community partnership.

The study involved 30 employee-stakeholders of the university from the different colleges in Pablo Borbon Campus. The researcher-made questionnaire served as the main data gathering instrument. Frequency, percentage and weighted mean were the statistical treatment utilized.

Findings of the study revealed that employee-stakeholders belong to 51 years old and above, female, with 21 to 25 years of service, a doctorate degree holder, associate professor in academic rank and enjoy faculty status. In relation to engagement to sustainability practices, it was revealed that since the university has taken initial preparations toward strong commitment to SDGs, results of study affirmed to a moderate extent of engagement with respect to teaching methods, policies and initiatives, sustainable university operations, and community partnership.

Keywords: *Batangas State University, Stakeholder's engagement, sustainability practices*

Transformative Learning: Lived Experiences of Secondary Physical Education Teachers in Managing Students' Injuries in Rural Areas

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative phenomenological research investigates the lived experiences of rural secondary public school physical education (PE) teachers as they deal with student injuries during PE lessons. Guided by Transformative Learning Theory, the study aims to: examine how PE teachers respond to injury incidents, identify the support systems available to them and challenges they face, identify how these experiences influence future teaching behaviors, and develop an effective injury management training program. Data were collected via face to face interviews with ten PE teachers, who are also first responders when student injuries occur. The results show that teachers go through emotional distress during incidents of injury, compounded by lack of training, resources, and institutional support. Some of the dominant themes include a change in pedagogy towards improved safety, the critical need for complete and practical first aid training, and the significance of emotional resilience in responding to injury. Generally, teachers also placed emphasis upon experiential situation-specific learning based on a mix of both psychological and technical preparedness. The study highlights the considerable impact of these experiences on teaching practices and the need for structured support systems as well as special professional development for rural physical education teachers. These results helped in crafting a training program and safer schools.

Keywords: *Transformative Learning, Phenomenological Research, First aid training, PE teachers' lived experience, Student Injury. Physical Education Teachers.*

Students' Engagement with Artificial Intelligence

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to investigate the level of personal and academic engagement of students with artificial intelligence (AI). The descriptive research design was utilized by the researchers. The study includes the analysis of students' engagement with AI when grouped according to their profile variables. The researchers chose 143 social studies students as respondents using the RaoSoft sample size calculator in order to collect samples from the population. The researchers used a survey questionnaire, administered personally as the main tool for gathering data. Data analysis involved the use of percentages, weighted mean, and p-values to interpret the results. After analyzing and interpreting the data gathered, the researchers found that the respondents showed higher levels of engagement with AI for personal use rather than for academic purposes. This observation highlights a growing trend among students, who seemingly prefer leveraging AI technologies for everyday tasks, entertainment, and personal productivity rather than for enhancing their academic performance. Moreover, there is no significant difference in personal engagement with AI in terms of gender, frequency of using AI, and socio-economic status, indicating that these factors do not play a substantial role in how students interact with AI on a personal level. However, there is a significant difference in personal engagement with AI concerning year level, suggesting that as students' progress through their academic journey, their interaction with AI tools may evolve, possibly due to increased familiarity or reliance on technology. Furthermore, the analysis revealed no significant difference in academic engagement with AI in terms of gender and frequency of using AI, yet it did indicate a notable difference in academic engagement concerning year level and socio-economic status. This finding may imply that students in different academic stages or from varying socio-economic backgrounds approach the use of AI in their studies differently, potentially influenced by access to technology or varying levels of digital literacy.

With the foregoing findings, a comprehensive handbook was meticulously prepared by the researchers, specifically tailored for Social Studies students at Batangas State University- The National Engineering University. This resource aims to elucidate how Artificial Intelligence (AI) impacts students' learning, problem-solving capabilities, and overall involvement in school activities. It will delve into both the advantages and challenges presented by AI in educational settings, examining aspects such as personalized learning experiences that cater to individual student needs, as well as critical concerns surrounding privacy, data security, and algorithmic bias that could influence educational outcomes. The handbook will not only provide practical guidelines on effectively incorporating AI tools into study routines but will also encourage students to critically analyze the implications of AI in their academic lives. By fostering a holistic understanding of both the potential benefits and drawbacks of AI, the researchers hope to equip students with the knowledge necessary to navigate this rapidly evolving technological landscape, ultimately empowering them to become informed users and responsible stewards of AI in their educational journeys.

Keywords: artificial intelligence; academic engagement; personal engagement; digital literacy; ai utilization

IoT-based Junk and Scrap Trading System: Integration of Machine Learning Algorithms for PET Bottle and Aluminum Appraisal

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ABSTRACT

IoT sorts and rates recyclable PET bottles and aluminum cans in e-Basura reverse vending machines. The article covers design, integration, and performance evaluation. The modular hardware-software includes a Raspberry Pi edge-computing vision module with a CNN for image-based material classification, a sensor-based input validation module with ultrasonic distance sensors, inductive proximity switches, and a 5 kg load cell with HX711 amplifier for real-time object detection and weight measurement. On a curated dataset of labeled PET and aluminum objects under different illumination and orientation, the CNN model had 94.3% classification accuracy and 3.7% false rejection. The load cell subsystem detects non-compliant products, such as overfilled or liquid-containing items, with $\pm 2g$ precision. Intermittent Arduino Uno sensor fusion and device coordination occurred via asynchronous serial connection to the main control unit. Remote SQLite servers wirelessly accepted user input, object metadata, and point allocations. City College of Calamba extended field testing demonstrated good operational efficiency: mean object processing time was 1.87 seconds, continuous throughput exceeded 65 items/hour without thermal or logical difficulties. Bin-level capacity monitoring, 80% GSM notifications, 100% SMS delivery. QR-coded thermal receipts and account-linked point-tracking increased user engagement. After two months of continuous deployment, the system was >98% up. E-Basura is reliable, scalable, and economical for real-time, automated trash segregation. Modular smart city integration and multi-material detection are conceivable.

Keywords: IoT-enabled system, Convolutional Neural Network, recyclables, Machine Learning Algorithms

Qualitative Research on Navigating the Use of AI in Aviation Curriculum

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ABSTRACT

Integrating artificial intelligence (AI) into aviation education significantly advances how future pilots and aviation professionals are trained. The methodology focuses on understanding the experiences and perspectives of educators and students. A qualitative approach allows researchers to explore the nuances of how AI can enhance teaching and learning in aviation education. The research design is centered around semi-structured interviews and focus groups, providing flexibility to probe deeper into participants' thoughts while ensuring that key topics are covered. Data collection methods involve gathering rich, descriptive narratives from participants, which can reveal their insights about AI's benefits and challenges in educational settings. Interviews with instructors might highlight their readiness to adapt to AI tools, while discussions with students could uncover their expectations and concerns regarding AI's role in their training. One prominent finding is that both educators and students recognize the potential of AI to enhance learning experiences, particularly in simulating real-world scenarios and improving decision-making skills. This suggests that curricula should incorporate AI-based tools and applications that reflect the current realities of the aviation industry. Recommendations for curriculum enhancement include introducing dedicated modules focusing on AI technologies, such as machine learning and data analysis, which are increasingly relevant in aviation. Educators should also consider hands-on training opportunities that allow students to work with AI systems in realistic settings. This practical approach will equip future aviation professionals with the skills to thrive in a tech-driven environment.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Aviation, Learning Experience, Curriculum, Curriculum Enhancement

A Keyword Analysis of Research Articles in Thai and International Journals: Insights into Content Focus and Writing Style

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ABSTRACT

Publishing research articles requires an understanding of the conventions and expectations within academic communities. This study investigates the linguistic and thematic characteristics of research articles published in Thai and international journals through keyword analysis. The goal is to identify differences in research content, methodological focus, and writing style between the two publishing contexts. Two corpora of research articles (RAs) were compiled for analysis. The Thai RA corpus (TRAs) consists of 93 articles from six TCI-indexed journals, totaling 528,545 tokens. The international RA corpus (IRAs) comprises 100 articles from five high-ranking journals listed in SCImago under Linguistics and Language, totaling 817,177 tokens. The RAs were published between 2011 and 2015, and were selected based on the presence of the keywords learning, linguistics, or teaching in titles, abstracts, or author keywords. Special issues were excluded to maintain content consistency across both corpora. Keyword analysis was conducted using corpus linguistics tools to uncover patterns in the frequency and distribution of key terms. The results show that international articles feature broader topics, more diverse analytical approaches, and greater use of metadiscourse—particularly interactional and argumentative features. In contrast, Thai articles tend to focus on narrower, more localized topics with an informative writing style and limited stylistic variation. The findings highlight the importance of aligning English for Academic Purposes (EAP) instruction with actual research writing practices. They offer pedagogical implications for researchers and students seeking to publish in international journals, especially in the fields of linguistics and language education.

Keywords: *keyword analysis; research articles; academic writing; Thai and international journals; metadiscourse features*

English Language Competencies Required by HR Professionals in the Digital Era

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ABSTRACT

In today's globalized and digitally connected business environment, English communication skills have become essential for human resource (HR) professionals, particularly those operating in multinational and multicultural settings. This study aims to examine the importance, frequency of use, self-rated proficiency, and fluency of English communication tasks required in HR roles. A total of 40 HR professionals from various organizational contexts participated in the study by completing an online questionnaire. The instrument, validated by experts and demonstrating high reliability (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.98), assessed 17 key English competencies relevant to HR functions in the digital era, including writing reports, conducting interviews, delivering presentations, and using HR software. The findings reveal that while participants generally consider English skills important and report frequent use—especially in written communication—they rate themselves as only moderately proficient and fluent in more complex tasks such as negotiation, legal documentation, and training facilitation. The results underscore the growing demand for targeted English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction to support HR professionals in performing effectively in international and digital workspaces. The study also highlights the variability in responses based on organizational context, suggesting a need for differentiated training strategies. These insights have implications for curriculum design, workplace training, and future research in business communication.

Keywords: *Human Resource professionals; digital workplace; English communication skills; training needs analysis; English for HR*

Development of Art Toy Souvenirs Reflecting Nakhon Ratchasima's Cultural Identity to Promote Cultural Products

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to develop souvenir products in the form of art toys by utilizing the cultural identity of Nakhon Ratchasima Province as the primary design concept. The research process involves studying the provincial identity, local culture, and indigenous products of Nakhon Ratchasima, followed by the design and prototype development of the art toys, as well as evaluating target consumers' satisfaction.

The resulting product is an art toy modeled as a Korat cat, a significant symbol of the province, depicted holding various iconic local specialties and souvenirs such as Korat noodles, Chinese sausage, and Korat silk. The integration of local identity with art toy design creates a distinctive product that effectively communicates cultural values. Moreover, the product has garnered high interest and satisfaction among consumers.

This study proposes a creative development approach for souvenir products that meets market demands while promoting the preservation and dissemination of Nakhon Ratchasima's local culture in a modern and accessible form.

Keywords: art toy, souvenir, local identity, Korat cat, Nakhon Ratchasima, cultural product

Arm Accessory Design Based on Colors and Patterns of Glazed Tiles at Wat Ratchabophit Sathitmahasimaram Ratchaworawihan, Thailand

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to study the colors and patterns of the glazed tiles at Wat Ratchabophit Sathitmahasimaram Ratchaworawihan for the design of arm accessories that reflect traditional Thai identity with a contemporary touch. This qualitative research collected data from documents and field studies, focusing on topics such as traditional Thai arm accessories and the colors and patterns of the temple's glazed tiles. The research process included on-site data collection at Wat Ratchabophit Sathitmahasimaram Ratchaworawihan to examine the colors and patterns of the tiles, as well as visits to museums to study Traditional Thai Jewelry. The collected information was then applied to the design of traditional-style arm accessories, adapting the colors and patterns from the tiles. The resulting designs were evaluated for consumer satisfaction in the final stage of the research.

The findings present guidelines for developing arm accessories by integrating traditional Thai styles with the colors and patterns of the glazed tiles from Wat Ratchabophit Sathitmahasimaram Ratchaworawihan as a foundation for design, emphasizing practical use in the present era. The research produced two arm accessory pieces, named "Pawalaem" and "Lukmai Plai Mue," in traditional Thai style. The overall consumer satisfaction with these pieces was at the highest level, clearly confirming that the characteristics of traditional Thai arm accessories, as well as the unique colors and patterns of the temple's glazed tiles, can be used to design distinctive jewelry. Furthermore, the study concludes that utilizing cultural capital to discover uniqueness for identity creation and product development shows promise for advancing the creative economy.

Keywords: arm accessories, glazed tiles, cultural capital, Wat Ratchabophit Sathitmahasimaram Ratchaworawihan

Examining the Relationship of Line Succession on the Family Businesses' Performance of Selected ABM Students at Emilio Aguinaldo College-Cavite

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ABSTRACT

Businesses' operating policies often change when ownership is transferred from one family to another. Frequently, blood relations, rather than merit, dictate privilege and duty, which can negatively impact the company. Therefore, developing the required ownership abilities is essential to ensuring success during family succession. When discussing succession, success and failure are two highly erratic outcomes. This study examined the relationship of line succession on the family businesses' performance on the selected ABM students at Emilio Aguinaldo College—Cavite. This research utilized a quantitative research method and correlational research design. The researchers used purposive sampling, defining criteria such family business owners who have seen or experienced nepotism or line succession in their own family enterprises. Majority of the respondents had a service type of family business, 1-3 years of business operation and eldest child roles in the family business. There is a significant relationship between the performance of the chosen ABM students' family businesses and their line of succession, as indicated by the moderate to high positive correlation of 0.69 (Pearson r). With an overall mean of 3.45 (Agree), transferring ownership affects the performance particularly the goals, priorities, vision and strategies of the family business as it changed to another family member. Because the leadership abilities of succeeding generations frequently coincide, line succession not only helps maintain the family's customs but also enhances performance, facilitating easier transitions and ongoing economic success. Hence, ownership rights' regulations can be implemented to eliminate biases through merit-based criteria, conflict resolution mechanism and equal rights among family members.

Keywords: *line succession, nepotism, ownership, family dynamics, inheritance*

The Relationship of Green Human Resource Management Practices to Attitude and Green Behavior of Employees in Food Manufacturing Companies in Imus City, Cavite

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted from April 2024 to January 2025 in Imus Cavite. The research study aimed to determine the relationship of green human resource management practices to the attitude and green behavior of employees in food manufacturing companies in Imus City, Cavite. This study examined three variables through descriptive analysis. To achieve this purpose, the researchers determined the (1) demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, tenure, educational attainment, position, and income. Additionally, (2) the level of implementation of Green HRM practices in terms of; green recruitment and selection, green training and development, green appraisal and performance management, green pay and rewards system, and green employee relations. It also identified the (3) attitude of the employees on green HRM in terms of; cognitive beliefs, affective states, and behavioral aspects. It also determined the (4) Green Behavior (GB) of the employees on Green HRM in terms of; green organizational citizenship behavior, green interpersonal citizenship behavior, and green official behavior. Furthermore, the researchers determined the (5) significant relationship between the level of implementation of green HRM practices and attitude. Lastly, (6) the relationship between the level of implementation of green HRM practices and green behavior.

The demographic profile of the employees was analyzed using frequency and percentage distribution. To assess the level of implementation of green HRM, attitude, and green behavior, the researchers used statistical tools such as Likert Scale, Weighted Mean, and Standard Deviation. Additionally, statistical tools including Spearman's Rank Correlation were used to determine relationships between Green human resource management practices, attitude, and green behavior, as well as the correlation between Green HRM practices on attitude and green behavior of the employees in food manufacturing companies in Imus City, Cavite.

The study revealed the relationship of green human resource management practices to attitude in terms of; cognitive beliefs, affective states, and behavioral aspect. Also, perceived effectiveness on green behavior in terms of; green organizational citizenship behavior, green interpersonal citizenship behavior, green official behavior. This signifies a positive relationship between attitude and green behavior on green human resource management practices. Overall, the study's findings revealed that companies that implement green human resource management practices contribute to environmental objectives but also create a more engaged, responsible, and motivated workforce.

Development and Acceptability of BRASSICA-RAPA Petchay-desal

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ABSTRACT

The study “Development and Acceptability BRASSICA-RAPA petchay-desal” aimed to develop and assess the acceptability of Pandesal with the main ingredient of brassica-rapa (petchay) powders. The pandesal formulations were subjected to sensory evaluation by a panel of untrained consumers to determine overall acceptability, taste, aroma, texture, and appearance.

Results revealed that adding petchay powders significantly influenced the sensory attributes of the Pandesal. While incorporating these ingredients enhanced the product's nutritional profile, it also affected its overall acceptability. The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the potential of developing pandesal products and serve as a basis for further research and product refinement.

The table presents an overview of petchay-desal ratings across taste, smell, texture, appearance, and price. Notably, the product achieved a satisfactory average rating of 4.04 across all categories. However, a closer look reveals that texture was where petchay-desal fell short of consumer expectations. While the overall Rating indicates general satisfaction, addressing the texture-related feedback could enhance product appeal and competitiveness in the market.

Development and Acceptability of Solanum Melongena Cookies

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ANALYN I. DIOLA

Adviser

ABSTRACT

The study “Development and Acceptability of Solanum Melongena Cookies” aimed to provide a standard recipe for eggplant cookies, determine the acceptable amount of eggplant powder to use in the cookie mixture, assess the overall desirability of eggplant cookies, and determine their market feasibility.

Eggplant cookies are not just a sweet treat but also a potential source of health benefits. By catering to children's taste preferences for sweetness, we can introduce them to the nutritional benefits of eggplant. Phytochemical analysis could reveal the presence of beneficial nutrients and antioxidants, making eggplant cookies a potential contributor to improved dietary intake.

The survey results showed that Recipe Control #2 (T1), which included 8 grams of eggplant powder, was the most favored and accepted. These findings suggest that eggplant cookies have a high potential for consumer acceptance and market success if introduced for sale.

Challenges and Assessment of Graduates' Self-Esteem Towards Related Job Opportunities

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ABSTRACT

The study was conducted from May to November 2022. All the respondents are the graduates of Cavite State University-Imus Campus; the respondents must be a graduate of 4 year course from 2018 to 2022. The study employed quantitative method, more specifically, descriptive statistics. Stratified sampling was the strategy used by the researchers, stratified sampling divides the population into subgroups that all share a common trait. To gather the data, survey questionnaire was used by the researchers. Descriptive and Pearson Correlation test was used to analyze the gathered raw data from 225 respondents. The analyses were based on 225 respondents from Cavite State University-Imus Campus, batch 2022, which made up 28.44%. The batch with the lowest perceived frequency was batch 2021 with 11.56%. Each students answered a Likert-scale type of questionnaire with strongly disagree as 1 to strongly agree as 4. In order to quantify the results, researchers used mean to eliminate random errors and to help a more accurate result in identifying the level of each variable. Results suggested reciprocal effects between graduates' challenges on seeking job opportunities and self-esteem. Out of the 225 participants, 130 (57.78%) said they have tried between one and three times. While 42 individuals (18.67%) indicated they have attempted the question six times or more. Overall, the findings indicate that job opportunities' challenges and self-esteem are interdependent.

Financial Literacy and Personal Financial Management Practices Among Working Young Adults in Selected Areas in Cavite

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ABSTRACT

Financial literacy is deemed more critical due to the increasing uncertainty with the emerging global economy, especially in making sound financial decisions, effective money management, and coping with financial pressures. This study is to: Specifically, it aims to fulfill the following objectives: (1) determine the socio-economic profile of the participants; (2) determine the percentage of working young adults' income allocated for savings, investment, spending on wants, expenses for needs, and payment for borrowings; (3) analyze the financial literacy of working young adults in selected areas in Cavite; (4) assess the personal financial management practices; (5) determine the significant difference in financial literacy and socio-economic profile; (6) determine the significant difference in personal financial practices and socio-economic profile. Descriptive-comparative research design was used to determine the significant differences between financial literacy and personal financial management to the socio-economic profile. In this study, it was found that there is no significant difference between financial literacy and personal financial management practices to their socio-economic profile in terms of residence, age, sex, and type of employment. Furthermore, it was also found that working young adults have a moderately high level of financial literacy and personal financial management was reflected as moderately low, wherein the participants showed that they do not engage too much in financial activities such as borrowings and investing.

Exploring Mental Health and Well-Being Among BPO Workers in Imus City, Cavite

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to explore the mental health and well-being of BPO workers . The respondents were the BPO Employees working in Imus City, Cavite. This study aimed to determine the following: (1) the demographic profile of the BPO employees working in Imus City, Cavite based on (a) age (b) sex (c) civil status (d) educational attainment (e) employment status (f) length of service: (2) the mental health condition of BPO employees in terms of: (a) anxiety (b) depression (c) behavioral control (d) emotional ties, and (e) life satisfaction: (3) the psychological well-being of BPO employees in terms of: (a) self-acceptance (b) environmental mastery (c) personal growth (d) autonomy (e) positive relations with others (f) purpose in life: and (4) if there's a significant relationship between the mental health status and well-being of BPO employees.

The study employed a quantitative method, more specifically, descriptive-correlational design. Non-probability sampling was used for sampling procedure. Survey questionnaires were used to gather data. Descriptive and inferential statistic were employed to analyze the gathered raw data from 366 respondents working in Imus City, Cavite.

The study revealed that the participants' mental health conditions were affected in terms of anxiety, depression, behavioral control most of the time. Moreover, emotional ties, and life satisfaction has an equivalent interpretation of some of the time. For the psychological well-being of BPO employees in terms of self-acceptance, environmental mastery, personal growth, autonomy, positive relations with others, and purpose in life has an equivalent interpretation of somewhat agree or somewhat affected. Moreover, it was found out that there is a moderate positive correlations between mental health and psychological well-being,

Keywords: *mental health, psychological well-being, BPO employees*

We are angel? Poetic collection “Loc’s poems”

Professor Dr. Loc Nguyen, PhD, Postdoc

Loc Nguyen’s Academic Network, Vietnam

Loc’s poems – this piece of work is dedicated to God, my family and friends. Ultimately, I dedicate this collection to our beautiful life as well as great poets who are angels among mundane world.

Selected collection LOC’S POEMS (THƠ LỘC) includes native poems in Vietnamese and Chinese, created by poet Loc Nguyen (Nguyễn Phước Lộc) from 1993 to 2022. These poems are classified into 9 collections and 1 verse narrative such as “Tặng”, “Ca dao blog”, “Chưa đặt tên”, “Lại chưa đặt tên”, “华语”, “Viết tiếp thơ ơi”, “Vẽ”, “Tình”, “Điều”, and “Lục Kiều thời @”.

My poems, which would rather lean forward melody than lean forward prosody, are half popular half academic, half elegant half vulgar, half deep half humorous, half queer half naive, half modern half ancient. There are mundane men with many careers, as well as many fairies, ghosts, heroes, nymphs in my poems. There are also tears, smiles, unreal stories, hot news and many things. I see myself in my poems and I will be very glad if catching you in my poems.

Sex-Related Differential Item Functioning in Mathematics Assessments: A Methodological Comparison of the Rasch Model and Logistic Regression

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ABSTRACT

In the realm of educational assessment, it is imperative to ensure that tests are equitable for all examinees. This research examined sex-related differential item functioning (DIF) on a mathematics test through two parametric DIF detection procedures: logistic regression and Rasch model. The 100-item test was tested for validity and reliability and administered to 188 college students majoring in Mathematics. Logistic regression, as analyzed by change in Nagelkerke R^2 , detected 25 items with moderate to large DIF, of which 9 had large effects ($\Delta R^2 > 0.070$). Of these, 8 of them were shown to be biased, suggesting construct-irrelevant benefits to a sex group. Applying the Rasch model and the ETS Delta scale ($|\text{deltaLord}| \geq 1.0$), 26 items had moderate to large DIF, 10 of which had large effects ($|\text{deltaLord}| \geq 1.5$). Four of these were subsequently confirmed as biased. These findings indicate possible fairness issues since the impacted items can create group-specific advantages not related to the trait being measured. Both methods detected similar levels of DIF, but logistic regression identified more biased items, indicating greater sensitivity. The Rasch model, with its stricter assumptions, offers a robust trait-centered approach for unidimensional assessments. Together, their complementary strengths support a more thorough DIF analysis. Moreover, the revised test—after the deletion of biased items—demonstrated enhanced construct and content validity. Internal consistency reliability coefficients demonstrated a consistent scale. Overall, the removal of potentially biased items improved the fairness and psychometric quality of the test, supporting the significance of DIF analysis in test development.

Keywords: *Differential Item Functioning (DIF), Logistic Regression, Rasch Model, Sex-Related DIF, Test Validity*

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